

The Geodesic Irredundant Sets in Graphs

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Abstract: For two vertices u and v of a connected graph G , the set $I[u, v]$ consists of all those vertices lying on $u - v$ geodesics in G . Given a set S of vertices of G , the union of all sets $I[u, v]$ for $u, v \in S$ is denoted by $I[S]$. A convex set S satisfies $I[S] = S$. The convex hull $[S]$ of S is the smallest convex set containing S . The hull number $h(G)$ is the minimum cardinality among the subsets S of V with $[S] = V$. In this paper, we introduce and study the geodesic irredundant number of a graph. A set S of vertices of G is a geodesic irredundant set if $u \notin I[S - \{u\}]$ for all $u \in S$ and the maximum cardinality of a geodesic irredundant set is its irredundant number $gir(G)$ of G . We determine the irredundant number of certain standard classes of graphs. Certain general properties of these concepts are studied. We characterize the classes of graphs of order n for which $gir(G) = 2$ or $gir(G) = n$ or $gir(G) = n - 1$, respectively. We prove that for any integers a and b with $2 \leq a \leq b$, there exists a connected graph G such that $h(G) = a$ and $gir(G) = b$. A graph H is called a maximum irredundant subgraph if there exists a graph G containing H as induced subgraph such that $V(H)$ is a maximum irredundant set in G . We characterize the class of maximum irredundant subgraphs.

Key Words: Interior vertex, extreme vertex, hull number, geodesic irredundant sets, irredundant number.

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§1. Introduction

By a graph $G = (V, E)$ we mean a finite undirected connected graph without loops or multiple edges. The distance $d(u, v)$ between two vertices u and v in a connected graph G is the length of a shortest $u - v$ path in G . An $u - v$ path of length $d(u, v)$ is called an $u - v$ geodesic. It is known that the distance is a metric on the vertex set V . The set $I[u, v]$ consists of all vertices lying on some $u - v$ geodesic of G , while for $S \subseteq V$, $I[S] = \bigcup_{u, v \in S} I[u, v]$. The set S is convex if $I[S] = S$. The convex hull $[S]$ is the smallest convex containing S . The convex hull $[S]$

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can also be formed from the sequence $\{I^k[S]\}$, $k \geq 0$, where $I^0[S] = S$, $I^1[S] = I[S]$ and $I^k[S] = I[I^{k-1}[S]]$ for $k \geq 2$. From some term on, this sequence must be constant. Let p be the smallest number such that $I^p[S] = I^{p+1}[S]$. Then $I^p[S]$ is the convex hull $[S]$. A set S of vertices of G is a *hull set* of G if $[S] = V$, and a hull set of minimum cardinality is a *minimum hull set* or *h-set* of G . The cardinality of a minimum hull set of G is the *hull number* $h(G)$ of G . To illustrate these concepts, consider the graph G in Figure 1.1 and the set $S = \{s, t, y\}$. Since $I[S] = \{s, t, u, v, w, x, y\}$ and $I^2[S] = V$, it follows that S is a hull set of G . In fact, S is a minimum hull set and so $h(G) = 3$.

Figure 1.1

A vertex x is an *extreme vertex* of G if the induced subgraph of the neighbors of x is complete or equivalently, $V - \{x\}$ is convex in G . The hull number is an important graph parameter. The hull number of a graph was introduced by Everett and Seidman [7] and further studied in [2, 3, 4, 5, 8].

These concepts have many applications in location theory and convexity theory. There are interesting applications of these concepts to the problem of designing the route for a shuttle and communication network design. For basic graph theoretic terminology, we refer to [6]. We also refer to [1] for results on distance in graphs.

If S is hull set of a connected graph G and $u, v \in S$, then each vertex of every $u - v$ geodesic of G belongs to $I[S]$. This gives the following observation.

Observation 1.1([3]) *Let S be a h-set of a connected graph G and let $u, v \in S$. If $w \neq (u, v)$ lies on a $u - v$ geodesic in G , then $w \notin S$.*

The above observation motivate us to study a new type of sets, called geodesic irredundant sets, which generalizes minimum hull sets in a graph. In the next section, we introduce and study geodesic irredundant sets and the irredundant number of a graph. The irredundant number of certain standard classes of graphs are determined. Various characterization results are proved.

Theorem 1.2([3]) *For integers $m, n \geq 2$, $h(K_{m,n}) = 2$.*

Theorem 1.3([3]) *Each extreme vertex of a connected graph G belongs to every hull set of G . In particular, if the set S of all extreme vertices is a hull set of G , then S is the unique h-set of G .*

§2. Geodesic Irredundant Sets in Graphs

Let S be a set of vertices in a connected graph G . A vertex v in S is called an *interior vertex* of S , if $v \in I[S - \{v\}]$. The set of all interior vertices of S is denoted by S^0 . It can be observe that if $S^0 = \emptyset$, then $T^0 = \emptyset$ for any subset T of S . A set S of vertices is called a *geodesic irredundant set* or simply *irredundant set* if $S^0 = \emptyset$. An irredundant set of maximum cardinality is called a *maximum irredundant set* or a *gir – set* of G . The cardinality of a *gir – set* is the *irredundant number* $gir(G)$ of G . It follows from Observation 1.1 that every minimum hull set of a connected graph G is an irredundant set in G and so we have that $2 \leq h(G) \leq gir(G) \leq n$, where n is the order of G . To illustrate these concepts, consider the graph G in Figure 2.1. Let $S = \{v_2, v_3, v_5\}$. Then it is clear that $S^0 = \emptyset$ and so S is an irredundant set. It can be easily verified that any set with four or more vertices is not an irredundant set of G and so $gir(G) = |S| = 3$. On the other hand, let $S' = \{v_1, v_4\}$. Then $I[S'] = V$ and so we have that $h(G) = 2$. Since the irredundant number of a disconnected graph is the sum of the irredundant numbers of its components, we are only concerned with connected graphs. One can note that for each integer n , there is only one connected graph of order n having the largest possible irredundant number, namely n , and this is the complete graph K_n .

Figure 2.1

Theorem 2.1 For a connected graph G of order n , $gir(G) = n$ if and only if $G = K_n$.

We determine the geodesic irredundant number of certain standard classes of graphs.

Proposition 2.2 For integers $m \geq n \geq 2$, $gir(K_{m,n}) = m$.

Proof It is clear that $gir(K_{2,2}) = 2$ and so we can assume that $m \geq 3$. Let V_1 and V_2 be the partite sets of $K_{m,n}$ with $|V_1| = m$ and $|V_2| = n$. Then it is obvious that both V_1 and V_2 are irredundant sets of $K_{m,n}$. Now, let S be any set of cardinality greater than m . Then $S \cap V_1 \neq \emptyset$ and $S \cap V_2 \neq \emptyset$. Since $|S| \geq 3$, it follows that either $|S \cap V_1| \geq 2$ or $|S \cap V_2| \geq 2$. This shows that $S^0 \neq \emptyset$ and hence $gir(K_{m,n}) = |V_1| = m$. \square

Proposition 2.3 For any cycle C_n ($n \geq 5$), $gir(C_n) = 3$.

Proof Let $S = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k\}$ be any set of vertices in C_n of cardinality $k \geq 4$. We prove that $S^0 \neq \emptyset$. Assume the contrary that $S^0 = \emptyset$. Then we consider the following two cases.

Case 1. n is even. Now, let v be the antipodal vertex of x_1 . If $v \in S$ and since $|S| \geq 4$, it

follows that $S^0 \neq \emptyset$. So we can assume that $v \notin S$. Let $P_1 : x_1 = u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{\frac{n}{2}+1} = v$ and $P_2 : x_1 = v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{\frac{n}{2}+1} = v$ be the two $x_1 - v$ geodesics in C_n . Since $S^0 = \emptyset$, without loss of generality we can assume that $x_2 = u_r \in P_1$; and $x_3 = v_s \in P_2$ and $x_4 = u_t \in P_1$. If $t < r$, then $x_4 \in S^0$; and if $t > r$, then $x_2 \in S^0$. This is a contradiction. Thus S is not an irredundant set and hence $gir(C_n) \leq 3$. Now, since $T = \{u_1, u_{\frac{n}{2}}, v_{\frac{n}{2}}\}$ is an irredundant set of cardinality 3, we have that $gir(C_n) = 3$.

Case 2. n is odd. Let $x_1 \in S$ and let v, v' be the two antipodal vertices of x_1 . Let $P_1 : x_1 = u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{\frac{n+1}{2}} = v'$ and $P_2 : x_1 = v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{\frac{n+1}{2}} = v$ be the $x_1 - v'$ and $x_1 - v$ geodesics in C_n , respectively. Since S is an irredundant set containing at least four vertices, it follows that either $v \notin S$ or $v' \notin S$.

Subcase 2.1 $v \notin S$ and $v' = x_2 \in S$. Then it is clear that $x_3, x_4 \notin P_1$ and so $x_3, x_4 \in P_2$. This implies that either $x_3 \in S^0$ or $x_4 \in S^0$. This leads to a contradiction to the fact that $S^0 = \emptyset$.

Subcase 2.2 $v \notin S$ and $v' \notin S$. Now, since $S^0 = \emptyset$, we have that P_1 contains at most one of x_2 and x_3 . Also, P_2 contains at most one of x_2 and x_3 . Hence without loss of generality, we may assume that $x_2 \in P_1$ and $x_3 \in P_2$. Now, since $|S| \geq 4$, as in Case 1, it follows that $S^0 \neq \emptyset$. This is impossible and hence $gir(C_n) \leq 3$. Now, since $T = \{x_1, v, v'\}$ is an irredundant set of C_n , we have that $gir(C_n) = 3$. \square

The irredundant number of a graph has certain properties that are also possessed by the hull number of a graph. In [6], it was shown that if G is a connected graph of order $n \geq 2$ and diameter d , then $h(G) \leq n - d + 1$. The same result is also true for the irredundant number of a graph.

Theorem 2.4 *Let G be a connected graph of order n and diameter d . Then $gir(G) \leq n - d + 1$.*

Proof Let S be any set of cardinality greater than $n - d + 1$. Let $P : u_0, u_1, \dots, u_d = v$ be a diametral path in G . Since $|S| > n - d + 1$, it follows that S contains at least three vertices from the diametral path P , say, u_i, u_j and u_k with $0 \leq i < j < k \leq d$. This implies that $u_j \in I[u_i, u_k]$ and so $S^0 \neq \emptyset$. Thus $gir(G) \leq n - d + 1$. \square

We determine $gir(T)$ for T a tree.

Theorem 2.5 *For any tree T with k end vertices, $gir(T) = k$.*

Proof Let S be a gir -set of T . Suppose that the set S contains a cut vertex, say, v of T . Let $C_1, C_2, \dots, C_l (l \geq 2)$ be the components of $T - v$. It is clear that each component C_i of $T - v$ contains at least one end vertex, say, u_i of T . Since S is an irredundant set of T containing the cut vertex v , without loss of generality, we may assume that $C_1 \cap S \neq \emptyset$ and $C_i \cap S = \emptyset$ for all $i = 2, 3, \dots, l$. First, we prove that $l = 2$. Otherwise, if $l \geq 3$, then the set $S' = (S - \{v\}) \cup \{u_2, u_3\}$ is an irredundant set in T with $|S'| = gir(G) + 1$. This is a contradiction. Hence $l = 2$. Now, let $S_1 = (S - \{v\}) \cup \{u_2\}$. Then S_1 is an irredundant set of cardinality $gir(G)$. Moreover, S_1 excludes the cut vertex v and includes a new end vertex u_2 . We can continue this process until the resultant gir -set has no cut vertices. This is possible

only when S has k vertices or less. Now, since the set of all end vertices of T is an irredundant set, the result follows. \square

A *caterpillar* is a tree of order 3 or more, the removal of whose end-vertices produces a path.

Theorem 2.6 For any non trivial tree T of order n and diameter d , $gir(T) = n - d + 1$ if and only if T is a caterpillar.

Proof Let T be any non trivial tree. Let u, v be two vertices in T such that $d(u, v) = d$; and let $P : u = v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{d-1}, v_d = v$ be a diametral path. Let k be the number of end vertices of T and l the number of internal vertices of T other than v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{d-1} . Then $d - 1 + l + k = n$. By Theorem 2.5, $gir(T) = k = n - d - l + 1$. Hence $gir(T) = n - d + 1$ if and only if $l = 0$, if and only if all the internal vertices of T lie on the diametral path P , if and only if T is a caterpillar. \square

Remark 2.7 Every minimum hull set of a connected graph G contains its extreme vertices. This is, in fact, true for non-minimum hull sets and follows directly from the fact that an extreme vertex v is either an initial or terminal vertex of any geodesic containing v . One might be led to believe that every maximum irredundant set of a graph G must contains its extreme vertices, but this is not so, as the graph G in Figure 2.2, the set $S = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4\}$ is the unique *gir*-set of G . Moreover, any irredundant set of G containing the extreme vertex u_5 is of cardinality less than or equal to 3.

Figure 2.2

Remark 2.8 In a connected graph G , cut vertices do not belong to any *h*-set of G . But cut vertices may belong to *gir*-sets of a graph. For the graph G in Figure 2.3, the set $S = \{u_1, u_2, u_3\}$ is an *gir*-set containing the cut vertex u_1 .

Figure 2.3

Theorem 2.9 *In a connected graph G , a cut vertex v belongs to an gir -set in G if and only if $G - v$ has exactly two components and at least one of them is K_1 .*

Proof First, let S be an gir -set of G containing the cut vertex v . Suppose that $G - v$ has three components, say C_1, C_2 and C_3 . Since S is an irredundant set containing the cut vertex v , it follows that S intersect with at most one of C_1, C_2 and C_3 . Assume without loss of generality that $S \cap V(C_2) = \emptyset$ and $S \cap V(C_3) = \emptyset$. Choose vertices x and y in G such that $x \in V(C_2)$ and $y \in V(C_3)$. Then it is obvious that the set $T = (S - \{v\}) \cup \{x, y\}$ is an irredundant set in G . This is a contradiction to the maximality of S . Hence $G - v$ has exactly two components, say C_1 and C_2 . Now, suppose that $C_1 \neq K_1$ and $C_2 \neq K_1$. Then as above, we have that $S \cap V(C_1) = \emptyset$ or $S \cap V(C_2) = \emptyset$. Since $|S| \geq 2$, we can assume that $S \cap V(C_1) \neq \emptyset$ and $S \cap V(C_2) = \emptyset$. Let x and y be any two distinct vertices in C_2 . Then the set $T = (S - \{v\}) \cup \{x, y\}$ is an irredundant set in G , which is impossible. Hence either $C_1 = K_1$ or $C_2 = K_1$. Conversely, suppose that $G - v$ has exactly two components, say, C_1 and C_2 such that $V(C_1) = \{u\}$. Let S be any gir -set of G . Suppose that $v \notin S$. Since S is a maximum irredundant set and $V(C_2)$ is convex in G , it follows that the vertex u belongs to S . This implies that the set $T = (S - \{u\}) \cup \{v\}$ is an irredundant set of cardinality $gir(G)$ containing the cut vertex v . Hence the result follows. \square

Next theorem is a characterization of classes of graphs G for which $gir(G) = 2$. The length of a shortest cycle in a connected graph G is the girth of G , denoted by $girth(G)$.

Theorem 2.10 *For a connected graph G , $gir(G) = 2$ if and only if $G = P_n$ or $G = C_4$.*

Proof If $G = P_n$ or $G = C_4$, then it follows from Theorem 2.5 and Proposition 2.2 that $gir(G) = 2$. Conversely, assume that $gir(G) = 2$. If G is acyclic, then it follows from Theorem 2.5 that $G = P_n$. So, assume that G contains cycles. First, we prove that $girth(G) = 4$. Suppose that $girth(G) = r \geq 5$. Let $C : u_1, u_2, \dots, u_r, u_1$ be a shortest cycle in G . If $r = 2n$, then it clear that $d(u_1, u_n) = n - 1$; $d(u_1, u_{n+2}) = n - 1$ and $d(u_n, u_{n+2}) = 2$. Hence it follows that the set $S = \{u_1, u_n, u_{n+2}\}$ is an irredundant set in G , which is a contradiction to the fact that $gir(G) = 2$. Similarly, if $r = 2n + 1$, then we have that $d(u_1, u_{n+1}) = n$; $d(u_1, u_{n+2}) = n$ and $d(u_{n+1}, u_{n+2}) = 1$. Hence it follows that the set $S = \{u_1, u_{n+1}, u_{n+2}\}$ is an irredundant set, which is also impossible. This implies that $girth(G) \leq 4$. Now, if $girth(G) = 3$, then there exist three mutually adjacent vertices in G , say, u, v and w and so G has an irredundant set of cardinality 3. Therefore, we have that $girth(G) = 4$. Let $C : u, v, w, x, u$ be a shortest cycle in G . If $G \neq C$, then without loss of generality, we can assume that there exists a vertex y in G such that $y \notin V(C)$ and y is adjacent to u in G . Since $girth(G) = 4$, it follows that y is not adjacent to both x and v . This shows that the set $T = \{x, y, v\}$ is an irredundant set in G , which leads to a contradiction. Hence we have that $G = C_4$. \square

For any connected graph G , we have that $2 \leq h(G) \leq gir(G)$. The following theorem is a realization of this result.

Theorem 2.11 *For every pair a, b of integers with $2 \leq a \leq b$, there exists a connected graph G such that $h(G) = a$ and $gir(G) = b$.*

Proof If $a = 2$, then it follows from Theorem 1.2 and Proposition 2.2 that $h(K_{2,b}) = 2$ and $gir(K_{2,b}) = b$. So, assume that $a > 2$. Let G be the graph obtained from the complete graph K_b with vertex set $V(K_b) = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_b\}$ by adding new vertices u and v ; and the edges $ux_i (1 \leq i \leq b - a + 2)$ and $vx_i (1 \leq i \leq b - a + 2)$. We first show that $h(G) = a$. Since the set $S = \{u, v, x_{b-a+3}, x_{b-a+4}, \dots, x_b\}$ of all extreme vertices of G is a hull set of G , it follows directly from Theorem 1.3 that $h(G) = |S| = a$. Also, it is clear that the set $T = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_b\}$ is an irredundant set and so $gir(G) \geq |T| = b$. Now, it follows from Theorems 2.1 and 3.1 that $gir(G) = b$. \square

§3. Maximum Irredundant Subgraphs

In this section, we present a characterization of graphs of order n having the irredundant number $n - 1$. By Theorem 2.5, the star $K_{1,n-1}$ of order $n \geq 3$, which can also be expressed as $K_1 + \overline{K_{n-1}}$, has irredundant number $n - 1$. Our characterization of graphs of order n having the irredundant number $n - 1$ shows that the class of stars can be generalized to produce all graphs having the irredundant number $n - 1$.

Theorem 3.1 *Let G be a connected graph of order n . Then $gir(G) = n - 1$ if and only if $G = K_1 + \bigcup_j m_j K_j$ with $\sum m_j \geq 2$ or $G = K_n - \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k\}$ with $1 \leq k \leq n - 3$, where e_i 's all are edges in K_n which are incident to a common vertex v .*

Proof Suppose that $G = K_1 + \bigcup_j m_j K_j$ and let v be the cut vertex of G . Then it is clear that $V - \{v\}$ is an irredundant set in G . Also, if $G = K_n - \{vx_1, vx_2, \dots, vx_k\}$, then $V - \{v\}$ is an irredundant set in G . Hence it follows from Theorem 2.1 that $gir(G) = n - 1$. Conversely, assume that $gir(G) = n - 1$, then it follows from Theorems 2.1 and 2.4 that $diam(G) = 2$ and so G contains interior vertices. We consider the following two cases.

Case 1. G has a unique interior vertex, say v . Choose vertices u and w both are different from v such that $v \in I[u, w]$. In this case, we prove that $G = K_1 + \bigcup_j m_j K_j$. For, if G has no cut vertices, then the vertices u and w lie on a common cycle C ; and so there exist vertices x, y and z on the cycle C such that $P : x, y, z$ is a geodesic of length 2 with $y \neq v$. This leads to a contradiction and hence G has cut vertices. Now, since every cut vertex of G is also an interior vertex, it follows that v is the only cut vertex in G . Since $diam(G) = 2$ and v is the unique interior vertex in G , we have that the vertex v must be adjacent to every other vertices in G . Now, let C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k ($k \geq 2$) be the components of $G - v$. We claim that each C_i is complete. Suppose there exists j with $1 \leq j \leq k$ such that $diam(C_j) \geq 2$. Then there exists a geodesic $Q : u_1, u_2, u_3$ in G with $u_2 \neq v$. This is a contradiction to the fact that v is the unique interior vertex in G . Hence each component of $G - v$ is complete and so $G = K_1 + \bigcup_j m_j K_j$.

Case 2. G has at least two interior vertices. Let S be an irredundant set of cardinality $n - 1$ and let $V - S = \{v\}$. We first claim that $\langle S \rangle$ is complete. If not, assume that there exist vertices x and y in S which are not adjacent in G . Then $d(x, y) = 2$. Also, since S is an irredundant set of cardinality $n - 1$, we have that v is the only vertex adjacent to both x and y in G . Moreover, one can observe that if u_1 and u_2 are non-adjacent vertices in S , then the

vertex v is only vertex adjacent to both u_1 and u_2 in G . Now, Since G contains at least two interior vertices, it follows that there exist vertices u and z in G such that $u \neq z$ and $z \in I[u, v]$. It follows from the above observation that the vertex u is adjacent to both x and y . Hence $u \in S^0$. This is a contradiction. Thus $\langle S \rangle$ is complete. Now, since G is connected. By Theorem 2.1, we have that $G = K_n - \{vx_1, vx_2, \dots, vx_k\}$. \square

We now introduce a concept that will turn out to be closely connected to the result already stated in this section. A graph H is called a *maximum irredundant subgraph*, if there exists a graph G containing H as an induced subgraph such that $V(H)$ is a maximum irredundant set of G . For example, consider the graphs H and G in Figure 3.1. It follows from Theorems 2.1 and 3.1 that the irredundant set $S = \{u, v, w\}$ is maximum in G , and H is an induced subgraph of G . Hence H is a maximum irredundant subgraph of the graph G . Also, by Theorem 3.1, for positive integers n_1, n_2, \dots, n_r with $r \geq 1$, the graph $K_{n_1} \cup K_{n_2} \cup \dots \cup K_{n_r}$ is a maximum irredundant subgraph. The analog concepts of minimum hull subgraph was studied in [3]. A graph H is a minimum hull subgraph if there exists a graph G containing H as an induced subgraph such that $V(H)$ is a minimum hull set of G . Next, we characterize the class of all maximum irredundant subgraphs.

Figure 3.1 $G \& H$

Theorem 3.2 *A non trivial graph H is a maximum irredundant subgraph of some connected graph if and only if every component of H is complete.*

Proof First, let H be a maximum irredundant subgraph of a connected graph G . Assume to the contrary, that H contains a component that is not complete. Then there exist $u, v \in V(H)$ such that $d_H(u, v) = 2$ and so H has at least one vertex, say, w different from both u and v such that w lies on some $u - v$ geodesic in H . This is a contradiction to the fact that $V(H)$ is an irredundant set in G . We now verify the converse. Let H be a graph such that every component of H is complete. If H is connected, then H is the maximum irredundant subgraph of H itself. Otherwise, $H = K_{n_1} \cup K_{n_2} \cup \dots \cup K_{n_r}$ for positive integers n_1, n_2, \dots, n_r , where $r \geq 2$. Let $G = K_1 + H$. Then by Theorem 3.1, $V(H)$ is a maximum irredundant set in G . This completes the proof. \square

We leave the following problem as open.

Problem 3.3 *Characterize the classes of graphs G for which $gir(G) = h(G)$.*

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